

Perceived Influence of Workshop Safety Skills for Enhanced Employability of Electrical/Electronic Students in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated perceived influence of workshop safety skills for enhanced employability of electrical/electronic students in Rivers State. Three specific objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. This study was carried out in Rivers State. The population of the study was 743 respondents comprising 603 students and 140 instructors from the four technical colleges in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 260 which represents 35 percent of the total population. Cluster sampling technique was used for the study to obtain the sample of the study. Each of the four technical colleges represents a cluster. 50 students were selected from each of the cluster making a sample size of 200 for students. While 15 instructors were selected from each of the clusters, totaling 60 instructors involved in the study. The instrument used for this study is titled Perceived Influence of Workshop Safety Standard Compliance on Students' Employability. The instrument was validated and tested for reliability using test-retest which gave 0.70 reliability coefficient. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation. z-test was used to test the significance of the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that workshop personnel safety standard compliance skills, workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills and workshop environmental safety standard compliance skills would influence students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State. The study therefore recommended that government should encourage non-governmental organizations (NGO) to sponsor and organize seminars, conferences, workshops and symposia for instructors and students in technical colleges in Rivers State to sensitize them on workshop safety standard as well as how the safety standard will improve students' employability.

Keywords: Influence, Workshop, Safety Skills, Enhanced Employability

INTRODUCTION

Education is a right of every individual; it unlocks the development of personal potentials of citizens of a country and the world at large. Education can also be described as a light, without which the entire nation will be in darkness. Okwelle and Ayonmike (2014) opined that education is acknowledged as a means for transforming and empowering communities. There are various forms of education which include among others technical, vocational education and training (TVET).

TVET is a form of education that involves the training and acquisition of multiple skills. Hence Okwelle (2013) stated that TVET is widely recognized as the most effective means of empowering the citizenry to stimulate sustainable national development, enhance employment, improve the quality of life, reduce poverty, limit the incidence of social vices due to joblessness and promote a culture of peace, freedom and democracy. Federal Government of Nigeria (2013) in her National Policy on Education stated that TVET is used as a comprehensive term referring to those aspects of educational processes involving, practical skills acquisition and training in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to

occupations in various sectors of economic and social life.

The objectives of TVET according to FGN (2013) include providing training for manpower development in applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advanced craft and technical levels among others. The attainment of these objectives is an important function of formal vocational and technical education institutions in Nigeria such as Polytechnics, Technical Colleges among others (National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2011).

Technical colleges are institutions where students are trained to acquire relevant knowledge and skills in different occupations for employment in the world of work. According to NBTE (2011) technical colleges are post primary institutions where students are giving full vocational training that will enable them acquire relevant knowledge, skills and attitude for paid or self-employment in various occupations in the world of work. Instructors who work in these technical colleges have a vital role to play in the technical college workshops by creating, caring and putting confidence in their students.

Technical college students according Okoye and Arimonu (2017) are trainees who offer vocational/technical courses in Technical Colleges in order to acquire basic scientific knowledge and practical and Technical skills through vocational and Technical training. These students are expected to graduate with the required workshop safety skills to enable them comply with the safety standards expected of them in the world of work, but in recent times, education stakeholders have expressed their concern over the poor performance of students in technical colleges (Nworlu-Elechi, 2013). Some blamed the school administrators (principals and teachers) while some blamed the students and their parents. Whoever is to be blamed, the fact remains that workshop safety standard compliance in Technical college organizational management has an influence on the employability of students.

Azodo and Dejujigbe (2013) defined a workshop as any building which contains tools equipment or machinery principally used for manufacturing, making or repairing things especially with the use of wood or metal. It comprises different shops like welding shop, electrical shop, building shop among others. Every workshop contains potential hazards therefore in performing a skillful job in the technical college workshop, safety needs to be practiced. Safety materials and safety trained individuals are usually required to enhance the growth and academic performance of the students. Safety refers to freedom from those hazards that can cause death, injury, occupational illness, damage to or loss of equipment or property, or damage to the environment (Emmanuel, Sagbara, James and Okechukwu 2016). In the opinion of Oranu (2012) safety is the ability to perform every simple task involved in a job without causing damage to tools, equipment, personnel or materials used in performing the task. Okon (2011) stated that safety is the art and science of identification, evaluation and controlling work place hazards.

Hazard may be defined as any substance that has the potentials to cause harm, ill-health or injury, damage to property, plant, products or the environment, losses or increased liabilities (Puyate, 2001). It is essential to identify hazard as a pre-requisite for accident prevention. Accident may be defined as a sudden, unplanned or unexpected occurrence which is capable of bringing about loss of life, pains, time wastage, environmental degradation or loss of resources (Azodo & Dejujigbe, 2013). Most accidents are caused by human carelessness and rarely occur by themselves. Accidents that occur can cause burns, limb deformities, and loss of life among others. This will make the school that at first plays the role as the place to gain

knowledge becomes a place that does not guarantee the students' safety in the workshop.

Technical and vocational education system in Nigeria is designed to train competent personnel that will fit into different sector of the economy. The graduates are expected carryout services, diagnose, tests and repairs as highlighted in the national curriculum of technical colleges that is in use all over the federation (Olayinka & Oyenuga, 2010). The speedy growth and changes taking place across the industrial sector has brought about competitions and challenges in today's economy in the area of high-tech technology, information system, marketing, manufacturing and services. Therefore, for workers to effectively function in these areas, they need to be highly knowledgeable in both "hard" technical skills and "soft" generic skills for the maintenance and services of the industry and society at large (Wan-Mohammed & Yunus, 2009). However, it is paramount to acknowledge the role of technical and vocational education to national development. The main focus of TVE is the training of individuals on technical skills within the fields of their study and related career. But the labor market across the globe is demanding individuals with both technical as well as employability skills for them to effectively function and become more relevant and successful (Bancino & Zevalkink, 2007). The importance of training and equipping individuals with personal skills and qualities for the purpose of employment cannot be overemphasized; it therefore requires collaborative efforts from all stake holders including the industry to fully develop and maintain the spirit for the production of competent graduates that will face the challenges of rapidly changing economy (Wye & Lim, 2009).

The international Labor Congress (ILC) at its 88th session in 2000, defined being employable as the ability to combine all the skill set, competencies as well as knowledge that enable individuals to acquire, maintain and contain the challenges of a job. Individuals are said to be employable when they acquire the components of employability skills through quality education and training in a broader way. These include Problem Solving, Planning and Organizing, Learning & Technology, Self-management, Team work Initiative and Enterprise and safety skills (David, 2008).

Workshop safety generally has been a topic of concern for educators, parents, and researchers for decades. It is important for students to have a safe learning environment to ensure they have the best possible opportunity to succeed academically. Researchers have agreed that in technical colleges, the right school safety encourages higher academic performance (Brand, Felner, Shim, Seitsinger, & Dumas, 2003). The authors further stated that students who perceived that they are

unsafe at school are less engaged in classroom activities resulting to poor academic performance. Conversely, students who feel safe exhibit fewer depressive symptoms, have fewer conduct problems, and are more likely to have positive peer interactions which will in turn result to positive academic performance (Watson, in Brand, Felner, Shim, Seitsinger, & Dumas, 2003). While some school environments feel friendly, inviting and supportive, others feel exclusionary, unwelcoming and often unsafe (Kutsyuruba, Klinger & Hussain 2015).

In producing students who are highly skilled in technical fields, there is need to equip them with workshop safety skills in support of their technical skills. Technical training is desirable and these students typically use the practical training workshop more frequent for their technical practices (Asnain, 2013). The author continued that while working in a workshop, safety aspects to be complied with include the safety of the person working, safety of the machinery, tools, equipment, workshop environment and other workers because compliance to workshop safety standard can contribute to equipping students with holistic technical education programme, thereby producing a competitive graduate suitable for job roles.

Workshop safety standard is the main focus when performing practical work in the college workshop. Asnain (2013) stated that the standard of safety education comes with effective skill development and that no student should be allowed to use any equipment or machine for any process until the student has been tested and certified satisfactory in compliance to workshop safety standard. Workshop safety standard compliance can be described as the state of being in accordance with established safety standards and regulations, or the process of becoming so (Ojimba, 2013). The standard of safety compliance is regulated by safety compliance section of the school or organizations, as well as government legislation and is monitored and enforced by these bodies to ensure strict compliance.

Fleury (2016) identified some challenges militating against changing behaviours and fostering a culture of compliance with workshop safety rules and regulations. Local, social and cultural barriers may inhibit a workshop manager, the students and others from complying with the best safety standards and security practices. Good compliance requires clear rules, policies, and processes that have been agreed on by the professional bodies, organizational leaders, safety and security officers or school workshop managers. To comply with workshop safety standard according to Ojimba (2012), safety rules and regulations in the workshop or workplace should be practiced from time

to time to ensure that the students do not take it for granted. In order to determine the perceived influence of workshop safety standard compliance on enhancing employability of electrical electronics students in technical colleges, there is need to conduct a study to ascertain if instructors and students comply with workshop safety standard and how it can influence students' employability.

Statement of the Problem

Workshops in technical colleges had continually experienced series of accidents due to the negative and poor handling of tools and equipment, failure to put on safety apparatus (Uwaifo, 2009). Thus, for a perfect safety operation free from accident and hazards in the workshop, the students need to possess safety practice skills with the aim to prevent or totally eliminate the occurrence of accidents in the workshop. Furthermore, Uwaifo (2009) opined that students working in the workshop often sustain injuries, damage tools and render electronic machines non-functional and ineffective during practical works. This can be attributed to noncompliance with safety rules and regulations in the workshop. These students are most times sub-charged for damages done to expensive tools, equipment and machines at the end of workshop exercise. These have necessitated the anxiety of some students to always obtain permission with the intent to be absent from practical classes in the technical education workshops, while others are left with the perception that workshop practical exercises are risky and hazardous to human life. Inability to observe workshop safety standard appropriately could make students unemployable especially in industries that believes much in safety compliance.

However, it is common to believe that these various accidents had occurred due to negligence or failure of instructors or students to comply with the workshop safety standard which definitely is perceived to have a negative influence on students' employability. One potential issue that arises when considering the influence of workshop safety standard compliance on students' employability is the lack of consistency in training and enforcement across different educational institutions. This inconsistency can lead to varying levels of preparedness among graduates, potentially affecting their ability to secure employment in industries that prioritize safety. Additionally, the lack of emphasis on safety standards in technical education programs may result in students not fully understanding the importance of compliance in the workplace, putting themselves and others at risk. Addressing these concerns and implementing more rigorous safety training programs could greatly improve students' chances of finding and maintaining employment in their

chosen field. It is in the light of these that the researcher conducted this study to determine the perceived influence of workshop safety standard compliance on academic performance of students in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the perceived influence of workshop safety standard compliance skill on students' employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the perceived influence of workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.
2. Determine the perceived influence of workshop personnel safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.
3. Determine the perceived influence of workshop environmental safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Research Questions

For the purpose of this study, the following research questions are posed;

1. What is the level of perceived influence on workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State?
2. What is the level of perceived influence on workshop personnel safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State?
3. What is the level of perceived influence on workshop environmental safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

For the purpose of this study, the following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance;

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of instructors and students on the perceived influence of workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of instructors and students on the perceived influence of workshop personnel safety standard

compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of instructors and students on the perceived influence of workshop environmental safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out in Rivers State. Rivers State is one of the thirty-six states in Nigeria. The state is geographically located in the eastern part of the Niger Delta region. Out of the one hundred and twenty-one technical colleges in Nigeria, Rivers State has four (Akaninwor, 2010). The domain ethnic groups are Ikwerre, Ogoni, Etche, Ekpeye, Ogba, Egbema, Ndoni, Andoni, Opobo, and Abua among others. Rivers State was selected for the study based on the fact that adequate sample size of vocational and technical students and instructors can be gotten from these technical colleges in the State. The population of the study comprised all students and instructors in vocational levels I, II and III of the four technical colleges in Rivers State. Six hundred and three (603) students and one hundred and forty (140) instructors make up the population. This gave rise to a total number of Seven hundred and forty-three (743) instructors and students of the four technical colleges in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 260 which represents 35 percent of the total population. Cluster sampling technique was used for the study to obtain the sample of the study. Each of the four technical colleges represents a cluster. 50 students were selected from each of the cluster making a sample size of 200 for students. While 15 instructors were selected from each of the clusters, totaling 60 instructors involved in the study. Hence the sample size of the study was 260 respondents comprising 200 students and 60 instructors. The instrument used for this study is titled Perceived Influence of Workshop Safety Standard Compliance on Students' Employability (PIWSSCSEPQ). The questionnaire items were developed by the researcher. The questionnaire was divided into three (3) sections namely A, B, and C respectively. Section A sought respondents' opinion on the workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance and students' employability. Section B sought respondents' opinion on the workshop personnel safety standard compliance and students' employability. Section C sought the respondents' opinion on workshop environment safety standard compliance and students' employability. To determine the validity of the instrument the questionnaire items were scrutinized by the researcher's supervisor and two experts from the Vocational and Technology Education Department of

Rivers State University. Their comments and corrections were incorporated in the construction of the final version of the instruments. The reliability of the instrument was established using test retest method. The instrument was administered to ten percent (10%) of the respondents in two technical colleges in Abia State which are outside the study area. The results of the test were correlated with the use of Person Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) and the coefficient value obtained was 0.70, which represented a good reliability coefficient for the study. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation. Z-test was used to test the significance of the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. To agree or disagree on any item in the questionnaire, a decision rule based on the real limits of numbers was used as follows:

follows:

2.50-4.00 Strongly Agreed (SA)

1.00-2.49 Disagreed (D)

For a decision to be reached, it was decided that an item with a calculated mean value equal or greater than 2.50 was agreed, and any item with a calculated mean value below 2.50 was disagreed. Standard deviation value close or wide apart was used to determine homogeneity in the perception of the respondents. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using z-test statistics. Decision was taken on whether to accept or reject the hypotheses based on the critical and calculated values of z. For calculated value of z(z_{cal}) less than the critical value of Z_{crit}, the hypothesis was accepted

RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the perceived influence of workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State?

Table 1: Perceived Influence of Workshop Tools and Equipment Safety Standard Compliance Skills on Students' Employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Instructors=60			Students=200		
		Mean	S.D	Rmks	Mean	S.D	Rmks
The following skills can help in students' employability							
1	Knowing how to store all power tools with their electrical cords rolled in a neat manner.	2.76	0.67	A	2.59	0.50	A
2	Ability to operate a machine safely by following adequate instruction in its use.	2.51	0.76	A	2.80	0.62	A
3	Ability to keep tools and equipment to their respective toolbox or storage area when not in use.	2.80	0.68	A	3.00	0.76	A
4	Possessing the ability to maintain equipment and manage inventory of equipment, spare parts and consumable materials.	2.59	0.72	A	2.81	0.74	A
6	ability to repair tools/equipment with minor problems can position students for employment	2.73	0.63	A	2.56	2.56	A
7	Ability to maintain tools and equipment in good condition always.	2.67	0.74	A	2.83	0.67	A
8	Ability to select the correct size of tools and equipment for each jobs.	2.59	0.73	A	2.80	0.65	A
9	Ability to utilise electric powered tools competently with less supervision.	3.02	0.57	A	2.71	0.81	A
10	Ability to instruct users on the proper and safe use of equipment appropriate to the task of hand.	2.89	0.64	A	3.07	0.76	A
Grand Mean & S.D.		2.73	0.68		2.80	0.90	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows the mean responses of the respondents on the perceived influence of workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers

State. The analysis of the study revealed that respondents agreed that the following skills can help in students' employability; knowing how to store all power tools with their electrical cords rolled in a neat

manner (2.76 & 2.59), ability to operate a machine safely by following adequate instruction in its use (2.51&2.80), ability to keep tools and equipment to their respective toolbox or storage area when not in use (2.80 & 3.00), possessing the ability to maintain equipment and manage inventory of equipment, spare parts and consumable materials (2.59&2.81), ability to repair tools/equipment with minor problems can position students for employment (2.73&2.56), ability to maintain tools and equipment in good condition

always (2.67&2.83), ability to select the correct size of tools and equipment for each jobs (2.59&2.80), ability to utilise electric powered tools competently with less supervision (3.02&2.71), ability to instruct users on the proper and safe use of equipment appropriate to the task of hand (2.89&3.07).

Research Question 2: What is the perceived influence of workshop personnel safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State?

Table 2: Perceived Influence of Workshop Personnel Safety Standard Compliance Skills on Students' Employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Instructors=60			Students=200		
		Mean	S.D	Rmks	Mean	S.D	Rmks
The following skills can help in students' employability							
1	Awareness of the dangers of drugs or alcohol in the workshop	3.51	0.63	A	3.31	0.72	A
2	Ability to wear Appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE) appropriately before engaging in any activity in the workshop.	2.56	0.74	A	2.78	0.72	A
3	Ability to prevent accident or damaged in the workshop through proactiveness	2.81	0.73	A	2.89	0.86	A
4	Ability to operate electrical equipment and machinery safely	2.79	0.88	A	2.94	0.64	A
5	Ability to provide first aid treatment on accidents, cut and abrasions in the workshop.	2.81	0.86	A	3.02	0.82	A
6	Being properly informed on reacting to any emergency in the workshop.	2.81	0.68	A	2.95	0.62	A
7	Ability to fight any fire incidents in the workshop	3.09	0.65	A	2.61	0.77	A
8	Awareness of safe operational methods of all workshop tools and equipments	3.20	0.71	A	3.11	0.71	A
Grand Mean and S.D		2.95	0.74		2.95	0.73	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows the mean responses of the respondents on the perceived influence of workshop personnel safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State. The analysis of the study revealed that respondents agreed that the following skills can help in students' employability; awareness of the dangers of drugs or alcohol in the workshop (3.51&3.31), ability to wear Appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE) appropriately before engaging in any activity in the workshop (2.56&2.78), ability to prevent accident or damaged in the workshop through proactiveness (2.81&2.89), ability to operate electrical equipment and

machinery safely (2.79&2.94), ability to provide first aid treatment on accidents, cut and abrasions in the workshop (2.81&3.02), being properly informed on reacting to any emergency in the workshop (2.81&2.95), ability to fight any fire incidents in the workshop (3.09&2.61) and awareness of safe operational methods of all workshop tools and equipment (3.20&3.11).

Research Question 3: What is the perceived influence of workshop environmental safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State?

Table 3: Perceived Influence of Workshop Environmental Safety Standard Compliance Skills on Students' Employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Instructors=60			Students=200		
		Mean	S.D	Rmks	Mean	S.D	Rmk
The following skills can help in students' employability							
1	Ability to maintain a safe, clean and well-organized working environment to promote workshop safety.	2.51	0.63	Agree	2.77	0.80	Agree
2	Ability to monitor and identify existing or potential workshop related problems to minimize accidents.	2.71	0.86	Agree	2.65	0.63	Agree
3	Ability to record every damage and breakage properly.	2.61	1.11	Agree	2.70	0.79	Agree
4	Ability to ensure that workshop waste are properly disposed carefully.	2.98	0.68	Agree	2.76	1.05	Agree
5	Unkept environment associated with filth dirt that can affects the safety conditions are quickly identified	2.97	1.08	Agree	3.02	0.81	Agree
6	Ability to tidy machines and work benches after each practical lesson.	3.23	0.86	Agree	3.20	0.75	Agree
7	Ability to properly place all waste materials such as metals cut-offs and scrapped parts in special metal scrap bins	2.81	1.03	Agree	2.78	1.11	Agree
8	Ability to use brush and pan to remove oily paper, cloths, filings from the workbench or floor	3.24	1.19	Agree	2.93	1.05	Agree
Grand Mean and S.D.		2.88	0.93		2.85	0.87	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 shows the mean responses of the respondents on the perceived influence of workshop environmental safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State. The analysis of the mean responses showed that instructors and students agreed that the following skills can help in students' employability; ability to maintain a safe, clean and well-organized working environment to promote workshop safety (2.51&2.77), ability to monitor and identify existing or potential workshop related problems to minimize accidents (2.71&2.65), ability to record every damages and breakages properly (2.61&2.70), students' disposes workshop wastes disposal carefully (2.98&2.76), unkept environment associated with filth

dirt that can affects the safety conditions are quickly identified (2.97& 3.02), ability to tidy machines and work benches after each practical lesson (3.23&3.20), ability to properly place all waste materials such as metals cut-offs and scrapped parts in special metal scrap bins (2.81&2.78), and ability to use brush and pan to remove oily paper, cloths, filings from the workbench or floor (3.24&2.93)

Test of Hypotheses

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of instructors and students on the perceived influence of workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-test Statistic on the Difference in the Mean Ratings on the on the Perceived Influence of Workshop Tools and Equipment Safety Standard Compliance Skills on Students' Employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	z-cal	z-crit	s/level	Decision
Instructors	60	2.73	0.68	258	0.59	1.96	0.05	Significant
Students	200	2.80	0.90					

Table 4 above, shows that z-calculated value of 0.59 is less than the z-critical value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance, and the degree of freedom of 258, indicating that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of instructors and students on the perceived influence of workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers

State. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted

H0₃: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of instructors and students on the perceived influence of workshop personnel safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State

Table 5: z-test Statistic on the Difference in the Mean Ratings on the on the Perceived Influence of Workshop Personnel Safety Standard Compliance Skillson Students' Employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	z-cal	z-crit	s/level	Decision
Instructors	60	2.95	0.74	258	0.10	1.96	0.05	Significant
Students	200	2.95	0.73					

Table 5 above, shows that z-calculated value of 0.10 is less than the z-critical value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance, and the degree of freedom of 258, indicating that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of instructors and students on the perceived influence of workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers

State. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

H0₃: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of instructors and students on the perceived influence of workshop environmental safety standard compliance skills on students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State.

Table 6: z-test Statistic on the Difference in the Mean Ratings on the on the Perceived Influence of Workshop Environmental Safety Standard Compliance Skills on Students' Employability in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	z-cal	z-crit	s/level	Decision
Instructors	60	2.88	0.93	258	0.38	1.96	0.05	Significant
Students	200	2.85	0.87					

Table 6 above, shows that z-calculated value of 0.38 is less than the z-critical value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance, and the degree of freedom of 258, indicating that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of instructors and students on the perceived influence of workshop environmental safety standard compliance skills on students'

employability in technical colleges in Rivers State. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted

Discussion of Findings

Findings from research question 1 as shown in table 1 indicated that the following workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills can enhance students' employability in technical colleges;

knowing how to store all power tools with their electrical cords rolled in a neat manner, ability to operate a machine safely by following adequate instruction in its use; ability to keep tools and equipment to their respective toolbox or storage area when not in use, possessing the ability to maintain equipment and manage inventory of equipment, spare parts and consumable materials; ability to repair tools/equipment with minor problems can position students for employment amongst others. The study is in line with Asodike and Nwabueze (2017) who asserted that most technical colleges' workshops and laboratories in Nigeria show unkempt environment associated with filth and dirt, which in turn affect the safety conditions of instructors and students. Such workshops environment according to Asodike and Nwabueze is responsible for accidents such as injury, damage to equipment among others which in turn result to poor academic achievement.

Secondly, from the study, it was found that awareness of the dangers of drugs or alcohol in the workshop, ability to wear appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE) appropriately before engaging in any activity in the workshop, ability to prevent accident or damaged in the workshop through proactiveness, ability to operate electrical equipment and machinery safely, ability to provide first aid treatment on accidents, cut and abrasions in the workshop can help to enhance students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State. The study is in coherence with Mullarkey (2013) who stated that despite the emphases on safety of personnel in the workshop, one major accident stemming from rule noncompliance is the workshop accident involving the personnel which always calls for questioning of the safety of the entire workshop environment. Mullarkey further stated that poor management of workshop personnel and facilities contributed to lots of accidents involving workshop personnel which include instructors, students among others. Under this workshop setting, academic performance of technical college students cannot be improved. The finding is also in agreement with Fleury (2016) who stated that fostering a culture of compliance with workshop safety standard on the workshop personnel are challenging. While emphasizing workshop safety rules and regulations in the curriculum of technical education programmes at all levels is an important step, more remains to be done to ensure strict compliance to workshop personnel safety

Lastly, the study found that ability to maintain a safe, clean and well-organized working environment to promote workshop safety, ability to monitor and identify existing or potential workshop related problems to minimize accidents; ability to record every damages

and breakages properly; ability to ensure that workshop waste are properly disposed carefully; unkempt environment associated with filth dirt that can affects the safety conditions are quickly identified can aid students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State. This finding agrees with Amadike, Nsikan and Sagbara (2016) who said that most of the students and the technical college instructors do not follow workshop tools and equipment safety guidelines that have been made. The findings are also in agreement with Mullarkey (2013) who stated that safety in some technical college workshops in Rivers State are more complicated due to the fact that the number of students who make use of the space, facilities and existing tools and equipment at one time are too much. It therefore becomes difficult for the academic performance of the students to be improved under this type of workshop safety condition.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that workshop personnel safety standard compliance skills, workshop tools and equipment safety standard compliance skills and workshop environmental safety standard compliance skills would influence students' employability in technical colleges in Rivers State

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that

1. Government should encourage non-governmental organizations (NGO) to sponsor and organize seminars, conferences, workshops and symposia for instructors and students in technical colleges in Rivers State to sensitize them on workshop safety standard as well as how the safety standard will improve students' employability.
2. Administrators of technical colleges should always organize programmes to ensure that instructors and students comply with workshop tools and equipment safety as these will help in addressing the issue of incessant accidents in the workshop resulting from noncompliance to safety rules.
3. Safety kits and equipment should be provided to workshop personnel by government and stakeholders as this will help minimize accidents in the workshop which will improve the students' students' employability.

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